

Papers, Please!

Developed by: Lucas Pope

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Keywords

Authoritarian Systems, Border Control, Bureaucracy, Dystopia, Empathy, Ethical Decision-making, Ethical Dilemmas, Immigration Law, Migration, Political Science, Workflow Simulation

Introduction

Papers, Please is a puzzle-simulation video game created by indie game developer Lucas Pope, developed and published through his production company, 3909 LLC. In *Papers, Please*, the player takes on the role of a border-crossing immigration officer in the fictional dystopian communist country of Arstotzka, which has been and continues to be in political conflict with its neighboring countries. The player must review travelers' passports and other supporting paperwork against a growing list of rules using tools and a guidebook. Tasks include allowing in those with the proper paperwork while rejecting those without all proper documents, detaining those with falsified information, and balancing personal finances for their family. It is directed at players interested in exploring a completely unfamiliar role as an immigration officer and experiencing the moral questions that may arise at work. *Papers, Please* can be regarded as an attempt to raise awareness of the process of converting human beings into a handful of documents, questioning the morality of this procedure.

Facts

Release date:	8 August 2013 (improved phone version released in 2022)
Developer:	Lucas Pope, 3909 LLC
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	1
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	Average round takes about 45 minutes, can be between 30 and 90 minutes, depending on the players' decisions
Languages:	14 languages, including German, English, Spanish, etc.
Environment:	A phone or laptop is sufficient.
Material:	No additional material necessary.
Price:	€5.99 in the App Store; €9.75 for the PC version; no further costs

Resonance & Criticism

Papers, Please received numerous awards and was especially praised for its sense of immersion, which produced a strong emotional effect on the player. It never scored lower than an 8 out of 10 in all major review journals (Edge, Eurogamer, GameSpot, IGN,...), won the Seumas McNally Grand Prize, "Excellence in Narrative", and "Excellence in Design" awards at the 2014 Independent Games Festival, the "Innovation Award" and "Best Downloadable Game" at the 2014 Game Developers Choice Awards and "Best Simulation Game" at the 2014 BAFTA Video Game Awards. Critics praised the game as an example of video games as an art form, creating a game environment that suits the situation and helps convey the protagonist's emotional world. Some critics remark that the game can be repetitive.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Papers, Please* (Lucas Pope, 3909 LLC). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creator.

The player in *Papers, Please* dives into the work life of an immigration inspector at a border checkpoint for the fictional country of Arstotzka in the year 1982.

As an inspector, the player is tasked with reviewing arrival documents. Every in-game day, new rules are added to the required documentation, and over time this makes the document-checking process increasingly complex (see Figure 1). Immigrants arrive at the checkpoint with their paperwork, and if discrepancies are discovered, the player may interrogate the applicant. They can demand missing documents, verify the applicant's fingerprints, and order full-body

scans. If incriminating evidence is discovered, the player may order the entrant arrested. If an arrest is not necessary, the player must stamp the passport to accept or deny entry. Should the player violate protocol, a warning will be issued in the player's booth, and after another mistake, fines will be applied. The player has a limited amount of real-time, representing a complete day shift at the checkpoint, to process as many arrivals as possible. At the end of the shift, the player earns money based on how many people have been processed (and bribes collected), minus the fines received, and then must decide on a simple budget to spend that money on rent, food, and heating for their family. If the player goes into debt, the game ends with a game over. Accepting bribes risks being discovered and imprisoned by the government. The player is challenged with moral dilemmas as the game progresses, such as allowing the supposed spouse of an immigrant through despite lacking complete papers at the risk of accepting a terrorist into the country. They will encounter members of a secret organization called EZIC. Granting/denying entry to EZIC agents affects the end of the game. The player can also choose to escape to a neighboring country, Obristan, to start a new life, with or without their family.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

On the surface, *Papers, Please* is a game about thorough examination and strict adherence to a precise process. While this does train the player's conscientiousness and ability to identify discrepancies, the underlying learning objective is rooted in the moral dilemma caused by the player's decisions. *Papers, Please* presents the player with constant moral choices, but makes it really hard to be a good person. While the player can waive the rules to reunite a couple, they do so at the expense of their own family, meaning they must decide whether they want to create a better world or look after themselves and their loved ones (Croshaw, 2013). The consequences of their choices are clearly shown in the game, for example, through newspaper articles, messages from the ministry of immigration, or because the subjects return and express their (dis)approval, sometimes also in monetary form. These decisions are implemented into the story, so there is no way to avoid them. No external teachers are needed for this game because the tutorial does a good job of explaining the mechanics, and it is generally not very complex, so that players will find their way quickly.

Effectiveness

The developer Lucas Pope stated that he did not intend to create an empathy game, but that empathy emerged as a product of the scenarios he implemented, which led to emotional engagement (Wells, 2016). Several factors enhance the game's immersive experience and, by extension, its learning potential. The game mechanics, particularly the financial balancing of basic survival needs and the explicit depiction of player choices and their consequences, contribute strongly to immersion. This immersion makes the moral questions feel weighty and serious, thereby supporting the learning process. *Papers, Please* thus tries to foster

understanding and empathy for people working in this field, as many players feel overwhelmed after only a few levels, while border officers perform this work every day.

Nevertheless, the effectiveness is heavily questioned by researchers like Jorge Peña, who argues that the setting of *Papers, Please* could even be considered counterproductive, proposing that the atmosphere of distrust decreases subjective norms and lowers intentions to help (Peña & Hernández Pérez, 2020).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Due to *Papers, Please*'s dystopian nature, the game may be unsettling for players. Especially for players who have had experiences with migration, the atmosphere of the game may induce bad memories or even trauma. Additionally, although Pope stated that he avoided including specific references to inspirations such as the Soviet Union or the border processes at the Berlin Wall (Cullen, 2014), similarities cannot be denied. This may negatively influence perceptions of this history and reinforce stereotypes. Studies have shown that the setting of the game actually decreases willingness to help immigrants (Peña et al., 2018). Lastly, the release was delayed due to a nudity problem (within the body scanner), but a censorship option was added.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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